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Automated Optimization of Intersections Using a Genetic Algorithm

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ABSTRACT Traffic jams in large cities, in addition to having a very high economic cost, cause an increase in emissions generated by vehicles over the same route being driven under normal conditions. In recent years, there has been a rapid evolution in the technologies applied to the field of autonomous vehicles. There are currently commercial solutions for assisted driving and semi-autonomous driving systems, with very favorable forecasts for reaching a completely autonomous vehicle scenario in the coming decades. This new environment generates opportunities and challenges to reduce congestion in scenarios with autonomous or semi-autonomous vehicles. This paper focuses on the automatic optimization of the passage of vehicles through intersections. The intersections are one of the most conflict-generating elements in a traffic network. This type of conflicts arises because the intersections must manage multiple traffic flows with different priorities and preferences, often leading to traffic jams. The problem has been addressed by proposing three mechanisms to model any type of intersection, to calculate the roads with fewer points of conflict between their inputs and outputs, and to optimize the arrival rate of vehicles using a Genetic Algorithm to achieve the maximum performance of the intersection. To validate this solution, a cellular automata simulator has been developed, which can be adapted to both autonomous and conventional vehicle scenarios and can provide realistic results when certain conditions are met. The results obtained have been compared with other traditional solutions (priority and traffic lights) using microscopic traffic simulations, and with those obtained in other studies showing the advantages of the proposed system. The proposed systems achieve a throughput improvement between 9.21% and 36.98% compared with the traditional solutions.

INDEX TERMS Autonomous systems, autonomous vehicles, genetic algorithms, traffic congestion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Congestion is one of the big problems to solve in large cities. The INRIX Global Traffic Scorecard [1] assesses the impact of congestion 24 hours a day in 1,360 cities in 38 countries over 5 continents and calculates its cost as \$461 billion in 2017, only considering data from the US, UK, and Germany.

Traffic problems are very heterogeneous in terms of either their causes or their consequences. Road congestion is one of the most frequent causes, but it is not the only one. When congestion occurs, necessary mitigation actions should be taken to ensure that its duration is minimized. Another approach is to anticipate the possible formation of this congestion and guide the actions adopted to try to avoid it.

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Due to the importance of the problem, there have been extensive efforts devoted to finding solutions for it. The successive advances in technology in this field have led to the design and implementation of solutions that improve upon the previous systems. During the eighties and nineties, the so-called Advanced Traffic Management Systems (ATMS) [2] were created, defined as the central nervous system of any transport system. ATMS receive and combine inputs from heterogeneous data sources and apply a series of algorithms to make technology-aided transportation decisions. These types of systems have evolved into an Intelligent Transportation System (ITS), which is the term commonly used today.

In the last years, improvements in technology in the field of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) have led to new opportunities to design and develop systems and tools focused on this new paradigm. The degree of autonomy

in driving a vehicle can be measured by levels using the scale defined by Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) [3], ranging from no driving automation (level 0) to full driving automation (level 5), in the context of motor vehicles. One of the most important factors which would enable the driving automation is the final price of the technology embedded in the vehicles. For instance, in [4], taking into account the changes in the price of technology and the current regulations, it is predicted that by the year 2030, about 98% of the vehicles will have connectivity. These forecasts lead us to be optimistic about the increase of autonomous vehicles and their automation level in the next decades.

One of the study areas explored in autonomous vehicles scenarios is the definition of new techniques applied to reduce the conflict points in a road network. These points are those places where various vehicles have planned to pass at the same time. Intersections are one of these points, and the management and coordination of the vehicles that cross through these points pose a challenge in any type of scenario. From the point of view of the efficiency of a route, the ideal case would be that a vehicle could cross through an intersection without having to stop at all.

This work is focused on optimizing the passage of vehicles through a generic intersection automatically. We do this by means of an automatic optimization system that achieves the maximum performance of an intersection in a CAV scenario. Our contributions in this field are described below:

- We create a model capable of univocally labeling all the elements that compose an intersection, in an automated manner, which allows to apply the approach proposed in this paper to any intersection regardless of type.
- We propose a process to calculate the shortest paths with minimum conflict points between them in a cellular automata scenario.
- We define an algorithm that obtains the patterns or cadence of the entry of vehicles into the intersection, using the previously calculated paths, to achieve maximum performance.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. First we will study intersection optimization alternatives such as: infrastructure designs that favor the passage of vehicles for a given way, management systems based on variable signaling, and optimizers that reduce the delays caused by intersections using bio-inspired algorithms (Section II). Starting with a known intersection, each of the components of the proposed system will be defined (cellular automata model for intersections, algorithm for calculating paths with minimum conflict points and optimizing crossing patterns through a Genetic Algorithm (GA) in Section III). The proposed system will be tested by analyzing the same intersection studied in [5] and [6] and comparing the results obtained with traditional intersection management methods as yield signs or traffic lights, which will validate its proper operation (Section IV). In conclusion, the advantages of the work will be highlighted and future lines of work will be indicated (Section V).

II. RELATED WORK

Intersection studies are among the most common studies in transport engineering [7]. “Although intersections constitute a small segment of the highway network, just under a quarter of fatal collisions occur there” [8]. These works focus on improving features such as intersection delay or queue length and saturation flow in its inputs. In this section, we will review some of the existing work on how to improve vehicle traffic through intersection optimization.

The management of the cross points between vehicles can be performed through conventional strategies based on intersections controlled by traffic signs (*e.g.* yield signs) or by traffic lights. Another common solution is the replacement of intersections for roundabouts [9]. From the intersection design perspective, there are also unconventional strategies to improve the efficiency and safety of intersections. Median U-Turn and Continuous-Flow intersections [10] are examples of this trend. The first one removes the left-turns from the main intersection (these movements are converted to right turns using a median crossover to make a U-turn). The second type shifts the left-turn from the surroundings of the main intersection to left-turns across the opposing traffic lanes located prior to the main intersection. Another solution based on the variation of the road structure is the proposal of Xie and Jiang [11]. In this work, they describe a model that incorporates the allocation of exit lanes as decision variables. Their design increases the capacity of isolated intersections. These strategies can help to improve the *a priori* traffic planning but present a high cost due to the need for building new infrastructures. Besides, they lack flexibility when the traffic flows vary.

The technological evolution has led to the rising of new scenarios based on the use of autonomous or semi-autonomous vehicles in a fully connected environment. Cooperative work among vehicles to use shared resources such as intersections has given birth to the field of Cooperative Intersection Management (CIM). Generally, these management systems can be classified as centralized or distributed. Another dimension for classification may be the use of signalized or non-signalized intersection [12].

There are systems designed to optimize the control of traffic signaling (signalized intersection) to achieve higher levels of efficiency. SCATS (Sydney Coordinated Adaptive Traffic System) [13] and SCOOT (Split, Cycle and Offset Optimization Technique) [14] are two systems based on the Urban Traffic Control (UTC) methodology. The intersections are monitored through detectors placed at their inputs and outputs.

Solving problems related to the cross points using the conventional infrastructures raise new challenges. Hult *et al.* [15], model the vehicle coordination as a finite time constrained optimal control problem. The authors focus on the combinatorial part of the problem, that is, the vehicle crossing order. They use a central optimization-based coordinator to manage the commands sent to vehicles.

Although the theoretical results obtained in this work are very solid, the algorithm proposed could present scalability issues in more complex scenarios.

It is a well-known issue that left turns reduces the intersection capacity significantly. Xuan *et al.* [16] propose a strategy based on grouping batches of vehicles depending on the turn they are going to take in the next intersection. They define a sorting area, before the intersection, where the set of batches are sorted to improve the efficiency of the intersection flows. The intersection input points are managed using traffic lights. This proposal improves the intersection capacity over conventional solutions, which are penalized by the left turns. Reference [17] follows a similar strategy, and also [18], where Yan *et al.* focus on solving this problem by optimizing the traffic light phases to enable left-turns. In general, these solutions present some drawbacks such as the cost related to requiring physical changes at the intersection in some cases. Additionally, in high congestion scenarios, the generation of batches depending on the turns taken by vehicles can be a very complex task.

Following the CIM classification, an example approach for a non-signalized intersection in a distributed system that uses many of the advantages achieved with the new communication technologies are “virtual traffic lights” (VTL) [19]. In these systems, vehicles follow the same operating principle of traditional traffic lights but instead of reacting to a light signal, all vehicles communicate with each other to decide cooperatively which direction has priority of passage. This system has many advantages as it allows to adapt to different traffic conditions, but it may have limitations due to the previously defined rules (necessary to define the vehicle with priority and the cycle time).

Azimi, in his PhD Thesis [5], analyzes multiple aspects of co-operative driving at intersections. He makes contributions to the management of V2V communications in these scenarios and develops tools such as his own simulator. Besides that, the chapters dedicated to vehicles synchronization in intersections are especially interesting. He defines in [6] “a spatiotemporal technique called the Ballroom Intersection Protocol (BRIP) to manage the safe and efficient passage of autonomous vehicles through intersections”. This strategy uses the advantages offered by V2X communications, and the vehicle geo-positioning to generate a set of Synchronized Intersection Arrival Patterns (SIAP). This allows him to, avoiding collisions, obtain the maximum possible throughput in the intersection. To validate his proposal, Azimi uses a cellular automata simulator based on a rectangular two-dimensional lattice with von Neumann neighborhoods. Although Azimi’s work is very extensive, it presents some limitations on how to apply these techniques to other intersection types.

Focusing on conventional intersection optimization works, the use of traffic lights is a widely studied solution, and there are many applied techniques. The improvement in sensor-based technologies, and especially in the Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) area, has offered new data sources which

can contribute to making more accurate decisions. The combination of WSN and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) has led to solutions such as the one proposed in [20] for the autonomous management of traffic light phases depending on real-time traffic conditions. Younes and Boukerche, in [21], work over the dynamic optimization of traffic lights scheduling in specific scenarios where there is a special priority for emergency vehicles.

A more general approach for connected vehicle scenarios is shown in [22], where they generate a co-operative system between vehicles and infrastructures, achieving, in most of cases, important improvements in the vehicle delays. The proposed solution, however, is based in a too ideal use case, although the results show the importance of this work.

The bio-inspired algorithms [23] applied to the optimization area, are very useful to obtain solutions over nonlinear complex problems. Like the previously referenced works, the optimization of vehicles crossing intersections through the traffic light control is a problem where bio-inspired algorithms can be useful. Chuo *et al.* [24] propose an enhanced particle swarm algorithm to determine a traffic signal timing plan between intersections. This allows the reduction of congestion in the network. This work has been tested in a simple scenario, obtaining good results, but presents some flaws when high congestion scenarios are reached. Similarly, Hao *et al.* approach this problem in [25] using a Tabu search-artificial bee colony algorithm which works under unsaturated flow conditions.

Genetic Algorithms (GA), one of the most popular bio-inspired techniques, have already been used to solve some of the problems referenced previously in this section. For instance, in [26] they propose a GA-based solution for the autonomous vehicle sequencing problem at intersections, and in [27] they offer a solution using GA for priority vehicles, specifically emergency vehicles, in intersections.

Finally, it is crucial in these studies to count on tools which allow to validate the proposed solutions. Traffic simulation tools have been developed to reach this goal and can be categorized in three types: Microscopic, Macroscopic and Mesoscopic [28]. For a detailed testing of the vehicle’s behavior, the most used simulators are the microscopic ones. Traffic cellular automata (TCA) models have proven to offer very reliable results with a high computational efficiency [29]. The usefulness of applying this type of models has been widely demonstrated in urban traffic scenarios. For instance, Tonguz *et al.* build an urban traffic mobility model in [30], where they also focus on the intersection control mechanisms. Other solutions such as [31] include in their model parameters like the vehicle speed, the braking lights, and the possible conflicts between traffic flows.

III. MODELING AND OPTIMIZATION OF INTERSECTIONS

The main goal of the proposed system is to obtain automatically the optimal arrival patterns, that is, the sets of routes and time intervals for vehicle arrivals to use an intersection as efficiently as possible. This efficiency is measured as

the intersection average occupation. That is, in a cellular automata-based scenario where vehicles do not stop or vary their speed, maximizing the average occupation of the intersection when all input flows are equal, implies maximizing the vehicle flows through the intersection as we will show in Section IV. Furthermore, if all vehicles move deterministically with constant speed, the system reaches a metastable state [32].

In this section, we explain in depth the proposed solutions to automate the problem management. We show the intersection modeling (Section III-A), the calculation of the possible less conflicting paths between inputs and outputs in the intersection (Section III-B) and then the GA developed to optimize the vehicle arrival rates which would maximize the average intersection occupation.

We have set a sample intersection to facilitate the comprehension of the proposals and developments, which allow us to show the application of the methods to a specific use case after the theoretical descriptions of each one. We have selected the intersection shown in Figure 1, being a recurrent example used in the literature [5], [17], [22], [27], [31]. This intersection is composed of 4 arms, with 3 input lanes and 3 output lanes each one.

FIGURE 1. Use case: Intersection composed of 4 arms with 3 input and 3 output lanes.

A. CELLULAR AUTOMATA MODEL FOR INTERSECTIONS

The Traffic Cellular Automata (TCA) are very efficient models to simulate microscopic traffic flows [29]. Therefore, they are frequently used in vehicular traffic scenarios, when it is important to analyze the behavior of traffic in a specific situation, such as the behavior of the traffic crossing an intersection.

There are diverse approaches to model a traffic scenario using TCA. There are various lattice topologies for a cellular automaton in two dimensions. Some of these types are triangular or isometric, and hexagonal, although the

use of a rectangular two-dimensional lattice is a common approach. In this kind of models, it is necessary to represent the turning restrictions derived from the intersection.

For Cellular Automata neighborhoods with a radius of 1, there are two possible models for rectangular two-dimensional lattice: the von Neumann or the Moore neighborhoods. The first one consists of the central cell itself plus 4 adjacent cells while the second one includes 8 adjacent cells.

In this work, we focus in an intersection modeling where each intersection is composed of cells of enough size to contain an entire vehicle and the mandatory security distances to the vehicles located in adjacent cells. Each cell contains the information needed for the vehicles to know the cells they can move to in the next simulation step.

Cellular automata modeling process for intersections has been divided into three phases: intersection grid generation from the geographical data, generic intersection modeling proposal and conversion from the proposed model to a directed graph. Figure 2 shows a graphical example of each step.

1) INTERSECTION GRID GENERATION

The first step to model the intersection is to generate the base grid using its defining features (shape, size, number of arms, number of lanes, distances between lanes, etc.). This grid will be used as the base of the cellular automata used to define the behavior of the vehicle in the intersection. Each cell of the grid must comply with minimum restrictions to guarantee the model correctness. The specific design features which should be taken into account to determine the cell size related with vehicles size, the possible conflict points, the turning radius, etc. have been covered in works such as [5, Ch. 7], [29, Sec. 1] or [31, Sec. 3].

Following the sample intersection is shown in Figure 1, and after applying the basic cellular automata modeling, the intersection is modeled as the grid shown in Figure 2.a. Each input or input lane in the intersection has been modeled as a fixed size cell sequence. Each vehicle can be located in one cell in each simulation instant and, in the next instant be moved to one of the adjacent cells, as long as the intersection rules allow it. The inner part of the intersection is composed by a cell grid which define the possible paths between inputs and outputs. In this case, the intersection geometry determines a 6x6 cell grid.

Although the example used throughout the article focuses on a TCA with very specific features, the modeling process proposed in section III-A.2 can be used in other types of environments. Section III-A.4 shows the application of this proposed modeling system to a TCA with smaller cells.

2) GENERIC INTERSECTION MODELING PROPOSAL

In step 1 we describe the generic process for transforming the traffic network into a TCA. The theory about simulators based on cellular automata does not cover the nomenclature to be used to identify the model elements, and usually, each

FIGURE 2. Intersection models. a) Cellular automata. b) Proposed system. c) Translation of the proposed model to a directed graph.

simulator uses a custom identifying system. One of the goals of this proposal is to provide a system able to automatically model the intersections of a traffic scenario. To achieve this, it is necessary to define a methodology which guarantees the unique denomination of each element in the model.

The proposal for the generic modeling is shown in Figure 2.b, and it is composed by the following steps:

- Identification of the input and output points in the intersection: Each arm in the intersection is a possible input point, output point, or input and output point for vehicles. The traffic flows can be then identified by these points, and therefore, they constitute the base elements of the model. The rest of the elements will be tagged according to these values.

The first arm to be tagged could be randomly selected, but we have decided to set criteria to be used in every intersection: The arm closest to the north will be selected as the first arm. If there is more than one arm at the same distance to the vector going from the center of the intersection to the north, we select the arm located in the right side of the vector as the first arm to be tagged. The next tags are assigned in order by following clockwise the next arms in the intersection. In the following sections, we use the combination of values given to each arm to tag the possible turns in the cells of the intersection. This means that the tags used for the arms must be selected in a way that allows to perform the opposite operation from the cell tag and obtain the possible turns. To allow this, we use base 2 exponents as arm tags:

$$Ta(j) = 2^j \tag{1}$$

where Ta is the tag of the arm and j is an integer between 0 and n , where 0 is assigned to the first arm and n is assigned to the last arm. According to this system, for the use case explained at the beginning of the section, we would have $Ta([0, 1, 2, 3]) = [1, 2, 4, 8]$, as shown in Figure 2.b.

- Input and output points tagging: The proposed intersection modeling system includes both the cells from the intersection itself and the first or last cell from the lanes that start or end at the intersection. That is, the cells used by vehicles when accessing the intersection or when they are leaving it. These cells are tagged from right to left in the direction of the traffic using integers and starting with 1. The notation for the cell tags is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{inputs} &: i_{ab} \\ \text{outputs} &: o_{ab} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where a is the value of the arm tag (Ta) and b is the lane where the cell is located. In Figure 2.b we show the tagged input and output cells using green and red colors respectively.

- Turning values in intersection inner cells: Once a vehicle arrives at a given cell in the intersection, one of the most important parameters to take into account by the simulator is whether the movement of the vehicle from the cell to any of the adjacent cells is allowed or not. This task can be eased using as cell values numbers composed by the addition of the values of each arm tag in the intersection where it is possible to move the vehicle to:

$$Tv = \sum_{k \in \text{PossibleTurns}(\text{CurrentCell})} Ta(k) \tag{3}$$

where $\text{PossibleTurns}(\text{CurrentCell})$ is the set of possible turns from the current cell to a specific output arm. In Figure 2.b, if from a given cell the vehicle can be moved to the left, we will add the value $Ta = 8$. If the vehicle can be moved towards the bottom of the intersection, the value $Ta = 4$ is added to the previous value, and therefore the cell value will be $Tv = 12$. For instance, if we select the inner top left cell of the use case intersection, we can see that in that cell the vehicle can go to the right (towards the arm tagged as 8), go straight (towards the arm tagged as 4) and turn to the left (towards the arm tagged as 2). Therefore, the turning

value for that cell is $Tv = Ta(1) + Ta(2) + Ta(3) = 2 + 4 + 8 = 14$. This value can be easily decomposed at any moment in the original base 2 exponents composing it and can be used to obtain the possible turns in the cell.

Following these previous steps, we can model the intersection completely. This process can be performed automatically using the geographic and geometric data of an intersection.

3) CELLULAR AUTOMATA TO DIRECTED GRAPH CONVERSION

The possible paths are taken by vehicles in the intersection (respecting the intersection restrictions) are a very important factor to optimize the intersection behavior. In Section III-B these paths are going to be calculated, and one of the most powerful tools to be used for the calculation of a high number of paths are graph based algorithms. In this section we show an algorithm for the transformation of the proposed cellular automata model shown in Section III-A.2 into a directed graph which can be used to obtain possible paths between input and output points.

The algorithm steps are:

- 1) Each cell in the original model is transformed into a graph node.
- 2) The turning values are retrieved by going through each cell in the model:
 - The values are decomposed in their base 2 exponents.
 - For each possible turn obtained in the previous point, the destination cell corresponding to the value is located and a new directed edge is added to the graph. The edge goes from the current cell to the adjacent cell in the direction pointed out by the turning value.

After carrying out this process, we obtain a graph composed by a set of nodes which correspond to the model cells and a set of directed edges which represent the possible movements between cells in the intersection. The result of the conversion process for the use case we have been following is shown in Figure 2.c.

4) MODELING IRREGULAR-SHAPE INTERSECTIONS

The use case shown in Figure 1 allows for the application of the proposal to a very specific scenario, which facilitates the explanation of the modeling process. Due to the characteristics of some intersections (number of input and output points, restrictions, or shape), it is possible that the TCA used in which each cell can contain a single vehicle is not possible. In these cases, the size of the cell can be reduced to adapt to the restrictions of the intersection, defining how many cells each vehicle will occupy (e.g. 1x2 cells per vehicle in [31]).

Figure 3.a shows a real intersection with five branches or arms. Each of these branches has a number of input and output lanes that vary between one and three. For each input lane, there are possibilities for turning by following the intersection's signage (the ability to go from each input lane to a specific output lane). This information is necessary

FIGURE 3. Model of an asymmetric five-branch intersection. a) Real intersection. b) Trip trajectories. c) Inner virtual lanes. d) Cells of the traffic cellular automata. e) Detail of turn values (virtual lanes). f) Detail of turn values (cells).

for the definition of the trajectories generated between each input lane and the possible output lanes in order to cross the intersection (Figure 3.b). The intersection model follows the same steps explained above in section III-A.2. It begins by listing each arm of the intersection, starting with the one farthest north, by successive powers of 2. In this case, a five-branch intersection, the values used are 1, 2, 4, 8, and 16. Due to the fact that the shape of the intersection and its input/output connections do not allow for a homogeneous grid, it is necessary to draw the set of virtual lanes based on the input and output paths (Figure 3.c). Similarly, one must define a cell size that fits both the dimension of the vehicles and the shape of the intersection, as well as the virtual lanes that have been defined. To this end, Figure 3.d shows a grid with cells measuring 1.5x1.5 m (i.e. each vehicle would occupy 2x3 cells).

After naming each of the intersection's arms and its input and output points, the third step of the proposed modeling system is to label each cell with the possible turn values.

Figure 3.e shows the turn values for each region of the previously-defined virtual lanes (e.g. starting from input point $i_{4/1}$, the first region has a value of 3, which allows the vehicles that use it to continue straight toward $o_{1/x}$, or turn right toward $o_{2/x}$). This assignment of turn values is transferred directly to the TCA so that each cell occupying the previously-labeled regions is given the same value. In the event that a cell occupies more than one region with different values, the assigned value will be that of the region that occupies the largest area of the cell. Finally, if two regions occupy the same area of the cell, the assigned value will be the one that coincides to a greater degree with the neighboring cells. This assignment is shown in Figure 3.f.

The movement of the vehicles follows the same principle described above but considering that each vehicle occupies six cells and that each of these cells must comply with the movement restrictions as defined by the labeling.

B. ALGORITHM FOR CALCULATING PATHS WITH MINIMUM CONFLICT POINTS

The vehicles cross intersections from an input point to an output point following a given path. If two paths have common cells, it is possible that at the same time more than one vehicle tries to occupy the cell. This generates a conflict point and forces stopping the simulation, because it would generate an invalid solution in which there would be a collision between vehicles, given that in this scenario the vehicle speed is a static value.

To obtain the greatest possible vehicle flow in the intersection, it is crucial to remove these conflict points. This can be achieved by generating paths without common cells or by modifying the vehicle arrival patterns, ensuring that there is not a time instant where there is more than one vehicle in a cell.

For each vehicle, there must be possible paths from its input point and to any output point in the intersection in each direction that is not the input direction, except if the intersection forbids a specific turn. In this case, it is not possible to generate completely disjoint paths without any common cell, but it is possible to calculate, using the proposed algorithm, the paths that offer the less possible conflict points. This guarantees that it is possible to optimize the vehicle arrival patterns and that we start from the best possible case in Section III-C.

We start the algorithm explanation by defining the set of elements to be used during the process. The set of possible ways or intersection arms (D) is shown in the Equation 4.

$$D = \{Ta(j) : j \text{ is an integer; and } 0 \leq j \leq n\} \quad (4)$$

where j identifies the specific arm, varying from 0 for the starting arm, to n for the last arm in the intersection, always following a clockwise order.

The set of input and output lanes in the way $Ta(j)$ are denoted by $L_{Ta(j)in}$ and $L_{Ta(j)out}$ respectively

(Equations 5 and 6).

$$L_{Ta(j)in} = \{i_{Ta(j)b} : b \text{ is an integer; and } 0 \leq b \leq m\} \quad (5)$$

where b is a integer between 1 (lane more to the right of the way) and m (lane more to the left of the way).

$$L_{Ta(j)out} = \{o_{Ta(j)b} : b \text{ is an integer; and } 0 \leq b \leq p\} \quad (6)$$

where b is a integer between 1 (lane more to the right of the way) and p (lane more to the left of the way).

Previously, we have defined the sets of elements of the intersection model proposed in Section III-A.2, which are necessary to obtain the paths with less conflicting points. The algorithm steps for the path calculation are:

- 1) An element $Ta(x) \in D$ is selected. This element is fixed as the starting input point of the intersection. The set I is composed by this unique element:

$$I = \{Ta(x)\} \quad (7)$$

- 2) O is the set of possible output ways, obtained as the difference between all the possible ways (D) and the way selected as input way (I). This set is shown in the Equation 8.

$$O = D - I \quad (8)$$

- 3) Let it be r the size of the set $L_{Ta(x)in}$. The permutations, with size r , of all possible output ways (O) are calculated and is denoted by $\mathfrak{S}(O)$. That is, $\mathfrak{S}(O)$ is composed by r -length tuples containing all possible orderings without repeated elements.
- 4) The Cartesian product of every set of lanes in each output way ($L_{Ta(y)out}$, where $y \in O$) in the intersection is calculated:

$$L_{product} = \prod_{y \in O} L_{Ta(y)out}$$

- 5) The Cartesian product of every set $\mathfrak{S}(O)$ and $L_{product}$ is calculated, and provides an ordered list of every possible combinations of output ways and lanes of each output way: $C = \mathfrak{S}(O) \times L_{product}$.
- 6) Each element $c \in C$ is composed by the combination of one output way $Ta(y)$, and one output lane of this specific $Ta(y)$. We calculate every possible shortest path between a fixed input way $Ta(x)$ (source node) and each c (target node), obtaining the set P_c .

Given that the size of each tuple in $\mathfrak{S}(O)$ is equal to the size of $L_{Ta(x)in}$, the selection of a specific input lane in $L_{Ta(x)in}$ as source node is determined by its index in the set (i.e.: if $L_{Ta(x)in} = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $O = \{2, 4, 8\}$, for a given element $(4, 8, 2) \in \mathfrak{S}(O)$, the input lanes 1, 2 and 3 have as destinations the ways 4, 8 and 2 respectively).

- 7) For each set P_c there is a matrix which is filled with the possible paths, obtaining the possible conflict points in the process. The number of possible conflicts is the cost of the specific combination of input and output points using the specific paths selected. The tuple formed by P_c and the calculated cost is added to the *paths* list.

- 8) The *paths* list is sorted from lower to higher cost. The element in the first position of the list is the set of input and output points in the intersection and their corresponding minimum conflict paths.
- 9) If the input flows are not symmetric (there is different traffic volume in each input way), the previous steps are repeated for the rest of elements in D .

In Figure 4 we show the results obtained by applying the algorithm to the use case of the paper. In this example, there is

FIGURE 4. Graphical representation of the optimal paths. a) Graph representing the intersection from the cells composing it. b, c, d, e) Minimum conflict paths for each input way. f) Representation of the conflict degree for each node (cell) in the graph: Green represents nodes without conflicts, yellow represents nodes with a single conflict and orange represents nodes with more than two conflicting routes.

an intersection composed of 4 arms or ways, and each one is composed of 3 input and 3 output lanes. Following the graph is shown in Figure 2.c, it is possible to determine that $D = \{1, 2, 4, 8\}$ and that $L_{Ta(j)_{in/out}} = \{1, 2, 3\}$, given that all the input or output ways are composed by the same number of lanes in this case. These features determine that the size of the set C for a single way is 162 ($6 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$) and therefore, the number of shortest paths for these 162 possible combinations is 81,067. Given that the size of D is 4, the size of the *paths* list is 324,268. The execution time for this algorithm applied to the use case has been 3.8242s (the testing equipment used for this calculations is the one described at the beginning of Section IV). In Figure 4, we show the graph modeling the intersection and the correspondence between this graph and the cell grid. In Figures 4.b, 4.c, 4.d and 4.e, we show the minimum conflict paths obtained for each input way in the intersection. Finally, in Figure 4 we show the conflict degree in each node when every route is used at the same time. Nodes without conflicts (there is zero or one route using the node) are colored green, nodes with a single conflict (there are two routes sharing the node) are colored yellow, and nodes with more than two conflicting routes are colored orange.

The paths calculated in this section are going to be used later in Section III-C.

C. OPTIMIZING CROSSING PATTERNS THROUGH A GENETIC ALGORITHM

In section II we have shown various methods for traffic flow optimization in intersections. Some of these methods, such as the one proposed by Azimi *et al.* [5], are based in the empirical study of a specific intersection type. Genetic Algorithm based optimization system proposed in this work, on the other hand, has been designed to be used in any intersection type and to be able to autonomously generate optimal solutions for each one.

Using the model proposed in Section III-A.2, each intersection has a set of input and output points denoted by i_{ab} and o_{ab} . These points are in the external perimeter of the intersection and, once a vehicle arrives at one of these points, following the cellular automata scenario, there is a fixed path crossing the intersection which leads to one of the output points (o_{ab}). While in the previous section the optimized calculation of these paths has been performed in an isolated manner, in this section we focus on obtaining the optimal input traffic flows to guarantee the maximum traffic rate in the intersection, without rising conflicts (collisions) between vehicles.

Genetic algorithms (GA), widely used to solve many complex problems in areas such as engineering or artificial intelligence, rely on the codification of the problem as an individual integrated into a population. Every individual is evaluated independently using a fitness function measuring the goodness of the individual according to the problem. This population, like what happens in nature, varies in each generation, favoring the survival of the individuals better adapted to the

environment (that is, the individuals which better solve the problem).

The arrival pattern in a cell i_{ab} determines the cadence of vehicle arrivals, that is, the time intervals between the arrival of vehicles to the intersection in that point. Although the size of the pattern can be from 2 to infinite cells, in symmetrical intersections they reach a stable state for patterns longer than the longest path run by the vehicles in the intersection. This stable state occurs when the sequence of occupation values is repeated every n simulation steps, where n is the pattern length. The set of vehicle queues of each input point (pattern) is the parameter to be optimized by the GA. Along with the codification of this problem, it is necessary to use a cellular automata-based simulator to validate the solutions obtained by each individual in each generation of the GA. This simulator is used to calculate the fitness value of the individuals in each iteration of the algorithm. In the next sections, we show the proposals for chromosome codification, the used GA, the methods used for selection, crossover and mutation, and the developed fitness function [33].

1) CHROMOSOME CODIFICATION

The codification of the problem must be carried out in a way that enables not only the evaluation of the individuals through the fitness function, but also to obtain viable crossover and mutation functions. In the case at hand, the variables of the problem are the sequences of vehicles composing the arrival patterns in each input cell of the intersection (i_{ab}). The following parameters define the codification of the individuals:

- The pattern is a sequence of bits and represents the input queues of vehicles to an intersection.
- The value 0 represents the absence of a vehicle, and the value 1 represents the presence of a vehicle in a tuple composed by a cell and a simulation step (*i.e.*: a queue of vehicles for a one input cell of the intersection with the pattern “vehicle - void - vehicle” would generate the sequence 101).
- The length of the patterns of each i_{ab} in the intersection is the same.
- Across the simulation, the pattern is repeated as much as it is necessary until all the simulation steps are completed.

The chromosome codification of the individual is shown in Figure 5. An intersection is composed of arms from 0 to n , where 0 is the arm selected as the first one to be tagged (the tag value will be 2 elevated to the arm number). We use 0 to start the numbering of the arms to follow the criteria of Section III-A.2. Each lane is numbered from 1 to m from right to left following the way that enters the intersection in each case. Finally, each lane is provided with a pattern of the same fixed length for every lane in the intersection. If the length of the pattern is l_p , the codification will be a sequence of bits of length $l_{ind} = (l_p \cdot m) \cdot (n + 1)$, where each bit position in the string represents the presence or absence of vehicles in a specific position in the input arm and lane.

FIGURE 5. Individual chromosome scheme using the values for input patterns in the intersection.

2) GENETIC ALGORITHM

The basic GA behavior is, starting from an initial population, the representation of the evolution of the population in the next generations. Following this principle, the steps of the algorithm are:

- 1) Initial population generation: For a pattern length l_p a random bit string of length l_{ind} is generated for every-one. The number of individuals in the population is an important parameter. If it is too small, there would be a low diversity between individuals, which would difficult the generation of a valid solution, and if it is too large, the search space would be too big, and the algorithm could get stuck in local minima (sub-optimal solutions).
- 2) The GA takes the current population and computes the next generation. This is performed by following the following steps:
 - a) Each individual in the current generation is evaluated using the fitness function. This function is described in Section III-C.4 and returns values between 0 and 1, where 0 represents the maximum average intersection occupation without collisions. In this case, the evaluation consists of a simulation for the input patterns proposed using the cellular

automata to obtain the occupation values for each simulation step.

- b) Every individual in the population is sorted from the lower (best value) to higher (worst value) results from the fitness function.
- c) The best individuals (elite) are automatically selected for the next generation.
- d) The rest of individuals are grouped in random couples and are combined using the crossover function. A new individual (child) of the next generation is created from parts of the chromosomes of each parent individual from the current generation.
- e) Finally, a small group of individuals from the current generation are mutated with random changes in the chromosomes. This process relies on a Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and a variable standard deviation.

The size of each set of individuals to be selected for the elite and crossover steps is defined as configuration parameters. The values used in this work are specified in Section IV-B.

- 3) The algorithm stores the best fitness value obtained in each generation and the differences in scores for every individual in the population.
- 4) The algorithm stops if one of the following conditions is met: i) A pre-established number of generations is reached (this limits the execution time of the algorithm), ii) The difference between the best fitness score and the average of a population is very low (there is no diversity between individuals), iii) The best possible fitness value is reached (0 in this case).
- 5) If the solution obtained at the end of algorithm execution generates collisions in the simulation, it is marked as invalid.

Given that in this problem there are two parameters to be optimized (the length of the pattern and the pattern itself), we have executed the GA repeatedly increasing l_p from 2 to the size of the maximum path which can be followed by a vehicle in the intersection. For each pattern length, the GA will obtain the pattern of that length which provides the lowest fitness value. At the end of the process, the lowest value of every pattern length tested will determine the best tuple of length and pattern.

3) CROSSOVER AND MUTATION

The crossover function takes two individuals (parents) of the population $p1$ and $p2$ (randomly selected from those not classified as elite individuals) and exchanges their genes (values in the bit string of the individual) to obtain a new individual $c1$ (child). The crossover is carried out randomly generating a crossover vector (cv) of the same length of the parents. The positions with ones in the vector are the bits which are taken from parent $p1$, and the positions of the zeros

determine the genes were taken from parent $p2$:

$$\begin{aligned} p1 &= [A \ B \ C \ D \ E \ F \ G] \\ p2 &= [a \ b \ c \ d \ e \ f \ g] \\ cv &= [1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1] \\ c1 &= [A \ B \ c \ d \ E \ f \ G] \end{aligned}$$

For the mutation function, we randomly select an individual from the population, and its genes are changed. The selected genes to be changed are selected using a Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and a standard deviation dependent on the individual size and the difference between individuals of the same generation. The result of this function is a new individual which is inserted in the next generation.

4) FITNESS FUNCTION

The fitness function design must take into account the goal set in Section III, which was the maximization of the average occupation of the intersection in order to maximize the vehicles flow through it. To achieve this, we have developed a cellular automata simulator that can simulate the vehicle behavior when crossing the intersection according to the proposed model.

This simulator takes as argument the intersection model (Section III-A.2), the optimized paths between inputs and outputs (section III-A.3) and the bit string corresponding to each individual in a GA generation. The simulator decomposes the string to obtain the patterns of each input point i_{ab} in the intersection and extends it to reach the total simulation time ($T = t_n - 1$). This time is calculated depending on the intersection size and the pattern. Each time instant in the simulation (step) represents the time that a vehicle spends in a cell of the intersection. As every vehicle has the same speed in the scenario, in each simulation step, the position of every vehicle is updated.

The intersection occupation can be variable along the time, so for measuring the average occupation we consider every occupation value only after the intersection reaches a stable state in t_i (that is, we do not use the first occupation values at the initial simulation steps, when the vehicles are still arriving at the intersection). We guarantee the correct calculation of the average occupation value \bar{o} by calculating it using the arithmetic mean of the partial occupation values ($o(t)$) from the instant when there has been a complete insertion of all the vehicles of a pattern (t_{stable}) and until the end of the simulation (t_{end}). This process to calculate the occupation is shown in the Equation 9.

$$\bar{o} = \frac{\sum_{i=t_{stable}}^{i=t_{end}} o(i)}{t_{end} - t_{stable} + 1} \quad (9)$$

The occupation value ($o(t)$) is measured in relationship to the maximum possible occupation (I_s) which depends on the number of cells composing the inner grid of the intersection. When two vehicles coincide in time and space during the simulation, there is a collision. We denote this collisions value

as C . Using these values, we generate the value F_V returned by the fitness function, following Equation 10.

$$F_V = \frac{(1 - \frac{\bar{o}}{I_s}) + \frac{C}{T}}{2} \quad (10)$$

The result of Equation 10 is a value between 0 and 1. For the maximum average intersection occupation without collisions it will return the minimum value ($F_V = 0$).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we show the experiments carried out to validate the proposed system. In order to compare the results with other solutions, we take as reference a specific intersection type and the results applied to that type found in related works. Additionally, we show the advantages of using a completely automated system for the modeling and optimization of the intersection behavior.

We start by recreating the results of one of the study cases carried out by Azimi *et al.* [5]. After that, we define the experiment we have carried out to apply the proposed system to that same use case, which would allow the comparison of the results obtained in each case.

In addition to the comparative study, we have adapted the test scenario to Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO) [34], a widely used microscopic and continuous road traffic simulation package. We have defined three simulation scenarios in which the intersection is managed using fixed signaling based on priorities, traffic lights, and the crossing patterns obtained in section IV-B (without signage). This set of tests will allow us to position the proposal in comparison to other systems that are widely used to manage traffic at intersections.

A. USE CASE BASED ON BRIP

In Section II the Ballroom Intersection Protocol (BRIP) [6] has been described. Among the intersection types described in Azimi's work, we have chosen the one named "multi-lane intersections of type III" (vehicles on the left lane must turn left, vehicles on the middle lane must go straight, and vehicles on the right lane must turn right). We have selected this type because it is the most complex scenario defined in that work. The author proposes using a Synchronized Intersection Arrival Pattern (SIAP) with a 5-unit length for that scenario. The SIAP proposed are, for each lane:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{right} &= [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1] \\ L_{middle} &= [0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0] \\ L_{left} &= [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \end{aligned}$$

If we translate these SIAP to the pattern of the model proposed we have:

$$P = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

In a symmetric intersection, this pattern would be repeated in each input. Azimi compares the obtained results for this pattern with the results of an intersection controlled by traffic

lights. The author states about these results: "BRIP outperforms the traffic light and stop sign models as it increases the parallelism and allows the simultaneous and continuous crossing of vehicles from all four directions". He includes a results graph which shows that in his simulation the delays (in seconds) of vehicles using his proposal are between a 90% and a 60% lower than using traffic lights.

For the comparison of the system proposed in this paper with the Azimi's work, we have used the pattern previously shown in the developed simulator. The obtained results show that the average occupation is $\bar{o} = 53.33\%$. The author uses the Intersection Capacity Utilization (ICU) concept, which is analogous to the \bar{o} definition in this work. Although for type III intersections Azimi establishes an ICU value of 56.25%, in appendix A-A we show the occupation values in each simulation step which confirm the value $\bar{o} = 53.33\%$.

B. EXPERIMENT DEFINITION

In this section we describe the experiment designed to validate the model described in Section III and compare it to Azimi's model.

The experiment uses a 6x6 cell intersection, with 4 input and output arms, and 3 lanes in each arm. The model generated for this intersection has been shown in Figure 2. The possible minimum conflict paths have been previously calculated and have been shown in Figure 4. Given that it is not possible to determine *a priori* the optimal length for the pattern, the experiment has been designed to search the best possible patterns with sizes from 2 to 14 (twice the length of the minimum conflict paths calculated) units.

Due to the use of GAs, which could lead to suboptimal solutions (the algorithm can stop at local minimums in the search space), we have repeated the GA execution 100 times for each pattern length. This allows the study of the solutions variability while obtaining results about the system performance.

The GA's set up for the experiment is:

- Pattern size: 2 to 14 units.
- Population size: 100 individuals.
- Max. generations: 150.
- Tolerance value (stop condition): 10^{-12} .
- Elite size: 5% of population size.
- Crossover size: 80% of population size.

The experiment has been carried out in a computer using MATLAB R2018a and the Global Optimization Toolbox for the GA development. The GA has been executed using the Parallel Computing Toolbox configured for 4 threads. The intersection modeling and the optimal paths have been implemented using Python 2.7 and the Numpy and NetworkX libraries. The computer specifications are Intel i7-7700 microprocessor with 32 GB (DDR4 2400 MHz) RAM memory and Ubuntu 18.04 operating system.

After running the proposed system over the use case under consideration, we obtain the results shown in Figure 6.

The reference value is drawn with a green dashed line and corresponds with to the average occupation value using

FIGURE 6. Average intersection occupations obtained for each pattern size by applying the proposed GA. The green dashed line represents the reference average occupation value for a 5 units pattern size. Red solid lines represent the median of every \bar{o} .

the Azimi proposal for a 5 units pattern size. This value is a 53.33%. For each set of average occupation values obtained for each pattern length, the graph shows, in red solid lines, the median of every \bar{o} . Additionally, for each pattern, the graph shows, in blue solid line boxes, the values between the 25 and the 75 percent of the data in each set. Finally, it shows the outliers with the “+” symbol.

The discussion of this results can be summarized in the following statements:

- The proposed system has been able to obtain automatically the same value than the solution proposed by Azimi, for the same pattern length.
- There are pattern lengths for which this proposal obtains better average occupation values than the Azimi’s solution. For a pattern size of 6 units, we obtain the best average occupation (57.407%). This value is an improvement of almost an 8% from the empirical solution provided by Azimi.
- The set of obtained solutions has a very low variability for patterns sizes from 2 to 11 units.
- When the system reaches a maximum average occupation value for a given pattern size, this same value is obtained for multiples of the size (for instance, for 5 and 10, or for 6 and 12).

In parallel, we have stored the execution times of the GA for each pattern size for the evaluation of the system’s performance. In Figure 7 it is shown the time in seconds spent on average (of the 100 repetitions of the execution) for each pattern size. An almost linear time increase can be observed when the search space is increased due to the pattern size variation.

C. SIMULATIONS BASED ON A TIME-CONTINUOUS MODEL

The primary objective of traffic simulators is to reproduce the behavior of drivers under certain conditions.

FIGURE 7. GA execution performance values for increasing pattern size.

Although SUMO can work with different models, the Krauss car following model [35] is the most common. Generally, the car following model is a method for determining how vehicles follow one another on a specific road. The Krauss model focuses on defining the desired velocity (v_{des}), taking a safe velocity (v_{safe}) into account. Calculating these velocities requires the use of values including the maximum deceleration possible, reaction time, the maximum velocity of the vehicle, and the time step.

A network has been created in order to adapt the simulation scenario proposed in section IV-B. It consists of an intersection featuring four branches, with three lanes per branch and direction. Due to the characteristics of the simulator, the input and output lanes of the intersection are defined with a length of 300 meters and with a maximum speed of 13.89 m/s (50 km/h). The vehicles are inserted at the start of the intersection’s input lanes at intervals of four, three, or two seconds (corresponding to low, medium, and high traffic volumes, respectively) following the vehicles pattern obtained through the previous experiment.

Three configurations have been made to manage the passage of vehicles through the intersection:

- Priority (*P*): The passage of vehicles is managed using yield signs along the horizontal direction of the intersection (see Figure 8.a). The vehicles traveling vertically have priority over the vehicles traveling horizontally.
- Traffic lights (*TL*): The intersection is managed by traffic lights with 42-second cycles. Vehicles that turn right from any outside lane have a green light throughout the cycle. The possibilities of continuing straight ahead or turning left are divided into periods of equal duration between the horizontal and vertical directions.
- Optimized crossing patterns (*OCP*): Following the proposed system, vehicles reduce their velocity and form groups that follow the patterns established in the meters leading up to the intersection. Velocity is reduced for safety reasons. Once they have crossed the intersection completely or partially (past the possible conflict points

FIGURE 8. Intersection management systems. a) Priority. b) Traffic lights. c) Optimized crossing patterns.

inside it), the vehicles accelerate in order to recover the maximum speed allowed by the system. A simulation is considered valid only if no collisions have occurred by its conclusion.

In order to measure the results of this set of simulations, we decided to carry out a scenario with the vehicles ending their trips between the simulation times of 0s and 3,600s. Since the three methods of managing the intersection involve inserting the same number of vehicles at low, medium, and high traffic volumes, the number of vehicles arriving at their destination gives us a valid system performance metric.

Table 1 shows the results that were obtained, grouped according to whether they resulted from low, medium, or high traffic volumes. Each result is labeled according the origin and destination of the trip and the type of movement it performs within the intersection.

TABLE 1. Simulation results based on the vehicles that have finished their trip during one hour. A total of nine simulations have been carried out combining intersections managed by priority (P), traffic lights (TL), and the optimized crossing patterns (OCP), and low, medium and high traffic volumes.

Turn type	From*	To*	Low			Medium			High		
			P	TL	OCP	P	TL	OCP	P	TL	OCP
Right	1	8	884	887	872	1181	1180	1255	1419	1255	1396
	2	1	887	886	880	1182	1181	1242	1418	1242	1408
	4	2	886	887	872	1180	1180	1250	1417	1250	1396
	8	4	843	887	872	1180	1179	1250	1417	1250	1396
Go straight ahead	1	4	355	440	437	474	586	804	708	804	873
	2	8	269	442	437	168	590	798	52	798	873
	4	1	354	440	438	473	586	796	710	796	877
	8	2	255	444	437	174	857	800	55	800	873
Left	1	2	178	147	146	237	196	189	354	189	291
	2	4	148	146	146	64	194	180	23	180	291
	4	8	177	147	146	236	196	179	354	179	291
	8	1	122	146	147	65	194	183	22	183	293

* 1,2,4, and 8 values correspond with the top, right, bottom, and left intersection sides, respectively.

Note: All values for P, TL and OCP are indicated in number of vehicles that finish their trips during simulation time.

Observing the values for the vehicles making a right turn (moving without interference), we can see how the value

obtained for all volume levels are very similar. For vehicles that continue to travel straight ahead, one can begin to see the effect caused by intersections that are managed based solely on priority. Even with low traffic volumes, the intersection’s vertical direction (1 to 4 and 4 to 1) allows more vehicles to pass than its horizontal direction (2 to 8 and 8 to 2). This effect becomes more significant as the traffic volume increases. Comparing the results of traffic lights with the proposed system for this type of movement, it can be observed that the proposed system always allows a greater number of vehicles to pass. Finally, the path that presents the most conflict points (turning left) maximizes the effects observed so far. The disparity between the different directions of the priority-based system becomes greater, and for high traffic volumes the number of vehicles managed by the proposed system is 50% higher than what can be achieved using traffic lights.

Summarizing the results, the OCP guarantees the input flows to the intersection are almost equal with a 5% of maximum difference. Furthermore, the proposed systems achieve a throughput improvement between 9.21% and 36.98% when compared with P and TL.

Although the advantages of the proposed system have already become evident, Figure 9 provides a graphic comparison of the results obtained for high traffic volumes, seeing as the experiment tests the intersection management systems at their limit. On the x-axis, we have the path followed by each vehicle within the intersection, as well as its branch of origin and destination. On the y-axis, we have the number of completed trips, or in other words, the vehicles that have reached their destination during the first hour of the simulation.

Using this graph, one can make several assertions:

- The paths without interference (turning right) present similar results under the three management systems.
- Both OCP and TL allow for equal use of the intersection among all vehicles, regardless of their point of origin. Meanwhile, the priority-based intersection creates a blockage situation for vehicles originating from nonpriority branches.

FIGURE 9. Simulation results for managed intersection with priorities, traffic lights, and the proposed solution (crossing patterns) in high traffic volume conditions.

- The proposed system offers the best average values for vehicles regardless of their origin or destination.
- The reduction in velocity required of vehicles under the proposed system in order to allow for the formation of groups is compensated for by the fact that it also provides a constant rate of vehicle passage.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have described an automated traffic intersection optimization system which is able to model, generate paths with a lower degree of interference between them, and optimize the arrival patterns of vehicles at an intersection, automatically to maximize their performance. Based on the objectives set in Section I, we can conclude the following:

- The proposed modeling system is capable, automatically, of labeling each element of any type of intersection univocally, containing the necessary information for the next steps of the system.
- The methodology proposed to calculate the shortest paths with minimum conflict points between them is capable of obtaining the best possible solution. The performance level of this methodology is very high. In the experiment performed, the methodology was able to calculate more than 80,000 routes in less than 4 seconds.
- The GA proposal used has shown its utility in getting to the same result for the same length of vehicle pattern as the reference work, but automatically. In addition, it has achieved better results using other pattern sizes.

In general, this system has provided better results than previous studies based on the empirical study of specific intersections, with the advantage that this method can be applied to any type of intersection. This factor is fundamental since, in a real traffic scenario, the number of intersections present in a road network can be very high and having an automatic optimization system facilitates the global optimization of the network. In addition, the comparison of the results with other traditional intersection management methods based on priorities and traffic lights shows the advantages of the proposed system.

This system has been designed to be generic, so that it can be applied to all sorts of intersections, not just those where the entrance flows are symmetrical. Our most immediate future work will be to study the variation the functions of the route calculations and the fitness function of the GA to prioritize specific flows at the intersection according to the convenience of the network design.

APPENDIX A GRAPHICAL RESULTS

In this appendix, we include the graphical results of the simulation steps carried out with the cellular automata model developed. In Figures 10 and 11 we show the occupation of cells composing the inner space of an intersection and the 5 cells closer to the intersection, associated to the input and output lanes. The white empty cells represent the absence of vehicles. The occupation value ($o(t)$) is shown over each simulation step, being t the current simulation step. In appendices V-A and V-B we explain the calculation of the average occupation value (\bar{o}) in each case, using the occupation values shown in the figures.

A. BRIP APPLIED TO TYPE III INTERSECTION

Figure 10 shows the results obtained when inserting the following 5 unit pattern in the intersection in a symmetric way:

$$P = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

Which, once decomposed in lanes, would be:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{right} &= [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1] \\ L_{middle} &= [0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0] \\ L_{left} &= [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \end{aligned}$$

When $t = 6$, all vehicles, following the pattern, have arrived at the cells adjacent to the inner intersection. Given that the maximum size obtained for the minimum conflict paths is 7 units, we must wait for 6 simulation steps to ensure that the vehicle following the longest path has been able to complete a cycle (from $t = 7$ to $t = 12$).

After $T = 12$, the simulation enters a stable state, where it will receive, in a repetitive way, the same input patterns. Is in this step ($t = 13$) where we start measuring the occupation values to obtain the average value during the simulation, which applying Equation 9 results as follows:

$$\bar{o} = \frac{\sum_{t=13}^{t=32} o(t)}{(32 - 13 + 1)} = 53.33\%$$

The simulation time is 12 units (step when the simulation enters the stable state) plus 4 times the pattern size.

B. PROPOSED SOLUTION APPLIED TO TYPE III INTERSECTION

Figure 11 shows the results obtained when inserting the following 6 unit pattern in the intersection in a symmetric way:

$$P = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

FIGURE 10. Graphical representation of the vehicles positions in each simulation step following the SIAP proposed by Azimi.

FIGURE 11. Graphical representation of the vehicles positions in each simulation step following the best pattern obtained in the carried-out experiments.

Which, once decomposed in lanes, would be:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{right} &= [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1] \\ L_{middle} &= [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \\ L_{left} &= [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \end{aligned}$$

Following the same reasoning than in the previous section, when $t = 6$, the vehicles, following the pattern, have arrived at the cells adjacent to the inner intersection. As in this case, the maximum size obtained for the minimum conflict paths is also 7 units, we must wait for these 7 simulation steps (the pattern length is greater than in the previous case) to ensure that the vehicle following the longest path has been able to complete a cycle (from $t = 7$ to $t = 13$).

After this instant, the simulation enters a stable state, where it will receive, in a repetitive way, the same input patterns. Is in this step ($t = 14$) where we start measuring the occupation values to obtain the average value during the simulation, being the calculation:

From $T = 14$, the simulation enters a stable state and therefore the process to obtain the average intersection occupation begins. For this pattern size, the simulation ends in $T = 37$. Applying these values to the Equation 9, the average occupation is:

$$\bar{o} = \frac{\sum_{t=14}^{37} o(t)}{(37 - 14 + 1)} = 57.407\%$$

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